

Supplement. RECORD reporting checklist (routinely collected data)

Reporting follows the RECORD statement, which extends STROBE for studies using routinely collected health data (Benchimol EI, et al. *PLoS Med.* 2015;12:e1001885). Item text is abbreviated; locations refer to sections of the main manuscript. BRFSS is a single survey program; no record linkage was performed, so linkage-specific items are marked accordingly.

Item	Recommendation	Reported in
RECORD 1.1	Type of data and name of the database in title or abstract	Abstract; Methods, Study design and reporting (2024 BRFSS)
RECORD 1.2	Geographic region and timeframe	Abstract; Methods, Data source and study population (US, 53 states and jurisdictions, 2024)
RECORD 1.3	Whether database linkage was conducted	Not applicable; no linkage (single survey program)
RECORD 6.1	Methods of population selection (codes or algorithms) listed in detail	Methods, Outcome (<code>_CRCREC3</code> eligible levels) and Data source and study population (age 45-75, positive design weight); variable crosswalk in repository

Item	Recommendation	Reported in
RECORD 6.2	Validation of the codes or algorithms used to select the population	Methods, Data source (CDC-calculated screening recommendation variable); BRFSS reliability and validity reference
RECORD 6.3	Flow diagram for the linkage process	Not applicable; no linkage
RECORD 7.1	Complete list of codes and algorithms for variables	Methods, Predictors; variable crosswalk in repository
RECORD 12.1	Extent of investigator access to the database population	Methods, Software, reproducibility, and ethics (public-use files; full eligible sample)
RECORD 12.2	Data cleaning methods	Methods, Missing data and survey weights (exclusions, in-fold imputation, encoding)
RECORD 12.3	Person- or institution-level linkage across databases	Not applicable; no cross-database linkage
RECORD 13.1	Selection of persons, including data-quality and availability filtering	Results, Sample and outcome; Methods, Data source and study population; analytic flow in repository

Item	Recommendation	Reported in
RECORD 19.1	Implications of using data not created to answer the research question	Discussion, Strengths and limitations (cross-sectional design, self-reported screening status, reduced-coverage and removed items, eligibility change from the 2021 USPSTF recommendation)
RECORD 22.1	How to access the protocol, raw data, or programming code	Methods, Software, reproducibility, and ethics (code and data dictionary openly available; BRFSS files from CDC)